

EFFECTS OF SILANE TREATMENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDROTHERMAL AGED GLASS FABRIC/ EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the effects of water immersion on the mechanical properties of glass fabric/epoxy laminates with different silane treatment. Both γ -aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (amino silane) and γ -methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (methacryl silane) were used as silane coupling agents. The weight loss occurred for the methacryl treated laminate, and as a result, the debondings at the interface with water penetration occurred. The changes of the mechanical properties were affected by only the degradation of the matrix in the amino treated laminate, while they were affected by the degradation of both the matrix and the interface in the methacryl treated laminate. The degradation of the interface induced the change of the fracture behavior due to water immersion.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) have excellent water resistance, and therefore have been often used in water environments. GFRP absorbs water in water environments, and as a result, a reduction of the mechanical properties is induced. Many studies have been performed for the degradation of GFRP in water environment [1-5], and some studies have reported that the property of the fiber/matrix interface has affected the degradation behavior of GFRP [6,7]. In previous works, some of the authors also clarified that the degradation of the fiber/matrix interface by the long-term immersion in hot water greatly affected the reduction of mechanical properties of glass fiber mat reinforced plastics [8,9].

In GFRP the fibers are generally treated by a silane coupling agent to enhance the bonding strength between fiber and matrix. The interfacial properties affect various mechanical properties, and therefore many studies have been done for the interfacial phenomena in GFRP [10-12]. However, these studies have dealt with the effect of the silane treatment on only the bonding strength between fiber and matrix, and the effect on the degradation behavior under environmental exposure has never been clarified.

In this study, the effects of fiber surface treatment by a silane coupling agent on the mechanical properties of glass fabric/epoxy laminates and the degradation behavior due to immersion in hot water are discussed. Two kinds of fiber surface treatment which are different in chemical reaction with epoxy resin are employed here, and the degradation behaviors of their laminates are evaluated by the weight change measurement and the changes of static tensile and impact flexural properties after immersion in hot distilled water.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials used were two kinds of plain woven glass fiber fabric/epoxy prepregs with different fiber surface treatment (SV-603 & S-502, Arisawa Manufacturing Co., Ltd., Japan). The plain woven fabric consisted of 19 strands/25mm in both longitudinal and transverse sections and the fiber strand consisted of 800 glass fiber filaments (9 μ m diameter). Both γ -aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (amino silane) and γ -methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (methacryl silane) were used as silane coupling agents. The amino silane has an organic function which can react with epoxy resin, while the methacryl silane does not have it. The laminates were fabricated by a compression molding method.

The weight changes were evaluated by weighing the specimens before and after immersion in water. The number of plies of the specimen was 6 for the weight change measurement. The geometry of the specimen was 50mm \times 50mm \times 1.2mm. The specimens were immersed in distilled water at 80°C for 5, 10, 25, 50, 100, 250 and 500h. The weight changes were evaluated by two parameters; weight gain due to water absorption (M_g) and weight loss due to dissolution (M_l). M_g and M_l are given by;

$$M_g = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_o}, \quad M_l = \frac{W_o - W_d}{W_o} \quad (1)$$

where W_o is the weight of dry specimen before immersion, W_w is the weight of wet specimen after immersion and W_d is the weight of re-dried specimen after immersion.

The effect of water immersion on the mechanical properties was evaluated by the tensile tests. The number of plies was 6 for the tensile test specimen, and the geometry of the specimen is shown in Fig.1. The specimens were immersed in distilled water at 80°C for 5, 10, 25, 50, 100, 250 and 500h. The tensile test was performed at a constant cross-head speed of 0.5mm/min by using an Instron universal testing machine (type 4206) under room temperature. After the tensile test the fracture surfaces of the specimens were observed by the scanning electron microscope in order to evaluate the changes of the fracture mechanism due to water immersion. In addition, the tensile test for 1 ply laminate was also performed to clarify the fracture process.

Figure 1. Geometry of the tensile test specimen.

The impact flexural test was also performed for the virgin specimens and the specimens immersed for 500h. The number of plies was 18 for the impact test specimen, and the geometry of the specimen was 100mm square and 4mm thick. In the impact test the specimen was clamped on all sides, and the center of the specimen was impacted by a striker with a hemispherical nose of 16mm diameter and 1.823kg weight. The incident impact energy was fixed to 3.3J/mm²-thickness (drop height was 0.74m).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

WEIGHT CHANGE

Fig.2 shows the changes of weight gain (M_g) as a function of the square root of immersion time. The changes of M_g for both the amino and the methacryl silane treated laminates showed the same tendency before 100h. They changed linearly against the square root of immersion time before

Figure 2. Changes of the weight gain, M_g , with the square root of immersion time.

Figure 3. Changes of the weight loss, M_i , with the square root of immersion time.

Figure 4. Appearances of 1 ply laminates before and after water immersion.

50h, and they approached the saturation at 100h. The saturation level of M_g was about 1.2%. M_g for the amino treated laminate remained almost constant after 100h, while that for the methacryl treated laminate increased again after 100h. Fig.3 shows the changes of weight loss (M_i) as a function of the square root of immersion time. M_i before 100h can be regarded as zero for both the amino and the methacryl treated laminates. M_i for the amino treated laminate kept almost zero even after 100h, while that for the methacryl treated laminate increased linearly against the square root of immersion time. In our previous work, it was clarified that the increase of M_i was caused by the degradation of the fiber/matrix interface [9]. Therefore it is considered that the serious degradation of the interface occurred after 100h for the methacryl treated laminate. On the other hand, the interface for the amino treated laminate kept good bonding even at longer immersion time. However, the scatter of M_i after 100h for the amino treated laminate may suggest the possibility of the degradation progress of the interface due to further immersion. Fig.4 is the appearances of 1 ply laminates before and after immersion. In the amino treated laminate, only the color of the matrix resin changed as a result of water. On the other hand, many debondings inside the fiber bundles could be observed in the methacryl treated laminate after immersion. Such debondings mean the change of the bonding state of the interface, and they occurred as a result of the dissolution from the interface which induced the increase of M_i . The water can penetrate easily into such debonded interface, and therefore, the possibility of re-increase of M_g is produced. The change of M_g due to such water penetration corresponded to the increase of M_g after 100h in the methacryl treated laminate.

TENSILE PROPERTIES

Tensile elastic modulus and strength for the virgin specimens are summarized in Table 1. The tensile modulus for the amino treated laminate was about 10% higher than that for the methacryl treated laminate. Tensile strength for the amino treated laminate also showed higher value than that for the methacryl treated laminate

Fig.5 shows the changes of the tensile modulus as a function of the square root of immersion time. The modulus for the amino treated laminate decreased little even after long term immersion. On the other hand, the modulus for the methacryl treated laminate gradually decreased to about 90% of the initial value up to 50h, and after that it kept almost constant value. It is considered that the reduction of the mechanical properties is closely related to the weight change behavior. Therefore the reduction mechanism of the modulus should be discussed from the view-point of the weight changes. Fig.6 shows the relation between the retention of tensile modulus and M_g . The modulus for the amino treated laminate decreased little with increase of M_g , while that for the methacryl treated laminate decreased linearly against M_g to 1.2% and remained constant afterward. The interface of the amino treated laminate kept a good bonding between fiber and matrix, and the modulus reduction was caused by only the modulus reduction of matrix resin as a result of water absorption. For the methacryl treated laminate the interface as well as matrix resin degraded gradually with the increase of M_g , and the modulus decreased greater in comparison with that for the amino treated laminate. After increasing M_i , the debonding occurred obviously inside the fiber bundles, and as a result, the modulus remained constant over 1.2% of M_g .

Table 1 Tensile properties for the virgin specimens.

Surface treatment	Tensile elastic modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Amino silane	22.5	465
Methacryl silane	20.6	406

Figure 5. Changes of the tensile modulus with the square root of immersion time.

Figure 6. Relation between the tensile modulus and the weight gain, M_g .

The changes of the tensile strength as a function of the square root of immersion time are shown in Fig.7. The strength decreased remarkably for both the amino and the methacryl treated laminates. The strength reduction process was classified into two stages (before and after 50h). The strength reduction for the methacryl treated laminate was more remarkable than that for the amino treated laminate before 50h. However, the strength reduction for the methacryl treated laminate after 50h was less than that for the amino treated laminate, and as a result, the retention of the strength at

Figure 7. Changes of the tensile strength with the square root of immersion time.

Figure 8. Relation between the tensile strength and the weight gain, M_g .

Figure 9. Fracture appearances of 1 ply laminates before and after water immersion under tensile loading.

500h showed almost the same value between the amino and the methacryl treated laminates. It is considered that the difference in the strength reduction process is also caused by the difference in the weight changes. Fig.8 shows the relation between the retention of tensile strength and M_g . The strength reduction process was classified below and over 1.2% of M_g . The strength reduction against M_g below 1.2% showed almost the same tendency both for the amino and the methacryl treated laminates, and the strength decreased linearly against M_g . Over 1.2% of M_g the strength also decreased linearly against M_g for the methacryl treated laminate, however, the strength reduction was remarkable compared with that below 1.2% of M_g . For the amino treated laminate M_g was almost constant at 1.2% at longer immersion time, however, the strength continuously decreased. Only the degradation of the matrix resin mainly occurred below 1.2% of M_g , while the degradation of the interface also occurred over 1.2% of M_g . Therefore it is considered that the cause of the strength reduction differs below and over 1.2% of M_g and the strength of the laminate is affected by its fracture process. Fig.9 is the fracture appearances of 1 ply laminates under tensile loading. For the amino treated laminate, large scale and long cracks occurred inside the weft fiber bundles in the virgin specimen, and two or three parallel cracks

progressed inside each fiber bundle. In the immersed specimen the number of such cracks decreased, and only a long crack without the parallel crack progressed inside each fiber bundle. The fracture mode changed slightly due to water immersion in the amino treated laminate. As mentioned above, the degradation of the interface did not occur in the amino treated laminate. Therefore it is considered that the main cause of the strength reduction is only the degradation of the matrix resin below 1.2% of M_g . However, the strength decreased continuously after reaching the saturation of M_g at 1.2%. Therefore it is considered that the strength reduction is caused by the occurrence of micro-debonding inside the fiber bundle, which never affects the weight change behavior. For the methacryl treated laminate, many cracks easily occurred inside the weft fiber bundles under tensile loading in the virgin specimen, and the multiple cracks occurred at very low stress level. As the degradation progressed due to water immersion, the debondings appeared only by the water immersion as shown in Fig.4. As a result, the cracks came to occur from such debondings at lower stress level in the immersed specimen. Consequently, the fracture mode also changed due to water immersion for the methacryl treated laminate. The debondings as shown in Fig.4 appeared over 1.2% of M_g because the remarkable dissolution from the interface occurred. Therefore the fracture mode changed below and over 1.2% of M_g for the methacryl treated laminate, and the strength reduction process also changed below and over 1.2% of M_g . These differences in the fracture mode produced the difference in the fracture surface. Fig.10 shows the fracture surfaces of the virgin specimens and the specimens immersed for 250h for 6 plies laminate. In the virgin specimens the fracture surfaces for the amino and the methacryl treated laminates were almost the same appearances. After the water immersion for 250h, almost the same fracture showed for the amino treated laminate, and a few loose fiber bundles could be observed on the fracture surfaces. Such loose fiber bundles may result from the occurrence of the micro-debonding due to water immersion. However, the fracture appearance for the methacryl treated laminate changed drastically after water immersion, and the loose weft and warp fiber bundles could be observed on the fracture surface of the specimen immersed for 250h. Such difference in the fracture surfaces was caused by the difference in the fracture process shown in Fig.9. As mentioned above, the bonding strength inside the fiber bundles gradually decreased below 1.2% of M_g for the methacryl treated laminate. In this process a few loose fiber bundles could be observed on the fracture surface. Over 1.2% of M_g the dissolution from the interface

Amino silane; virgin

Methacryl silane; virgin

Amino silane; immersed for 250h

Methacryl silane; immersed for 250h

Figure 10. Scanning electron micrographs of the cross-section of the specimen after tensile test.

occurred and the bonding strength decreased remarkably, and therefore many loose fiber bundles could be observed on the fracture surface.

IMPACT PROPERTY

Table 2 summarizes the energy absorption ratio (absorbed energy/incident energy) obtained by the impact tests. In the virgin specimens, the energy absorption ratio for the amino treated laminate showed a little higher than that for the methacryl treated laminate. Fig.11 illustrates the damages at the bottom face of the specimens after impact. The same type of the cracks shown in Fig.9(a) could be observed at the crack region in the amino treated virgin specimen, and the cracks spread in both the weft and the warp fiber bundles around the impact point. Moreover many fiber breakages could be also observed at the bottom face against the impact load. The fiber breakage was caused by the propagation of the large scale cracks. In the methacryl treated laminate the multiple cracks shown in Fig.9(c) could be observed at the multiple crack region, and such cracks spread widely around the impact point. However, few fiber breakages could be observed for the methacryl treated laminate. The scale of the cracks in the methacryl treated laminate was much smaller than that in the amino treated laminate, and such cracks never induced the fiber breakage. Therefore the impact energy is absorbed by the crack generation and by the fiber breakage due to the crack propagation for the amino treated laminate, while it is absorbed by only the multiple crack generation for the methacryl treated laminate. It is considered that such differences in the damage propagation induce the difference in the energy absorption ratio due to the silane treatment.

In the immersed specimens, the energy absorption ratio for the methacryl treated laminate showed much higher than that for the amino treated laminate, and this result was quite reverse of the result in the virgin specimens. The fiber breakage occurred at the bottom face both for the amino and the methacryl treated laminates immersed in water. The area where the fiber breakage occurred for the

Table 2 Energy absorption ratio in the impact test.

Surface treatment	Immersion time	Maximum deflection	Energy absorption ratio
Amino silane	0 h	4.441 mm	0.536
Amino silane	500 h	4.390 mm	0.702
Methacryl silane	0 h	4.647 mm	0.472
Methacryl silane	500 h	7.528 mm	0.846

Fig.11 Damage propagation at the bottom face of the laminates after impact loading.

methacryl treated laminate was much larger than that for the amino treated laminate. For the methacryl treated laminate the maximum deflection was much larger than those of the other laminates. It is considered that the large deflection in the methacryl immersed laminate results from the degradation of the interface, and it induces the fiber breakages at the bottom face. Such remarkable fiber breakages led to the higher impact energy absorption ratio. For the amino treated laminate, the enlargement of the area where fiber breakage occurred was caused by only the degradation of the matrix resin, and therefore the energy absorption ratio was smaller than that for the methacryl treated laminate.

CONCLUSION

This study dealt with the effects of the water immersion on the mechanical properties of glass fabric/epoxy laminates with different silane treatment of fiber. The specimens were immersed in hot water, and the weight changes, and the changes of the static tensile properties and the impact flexural properties were measured. The weight loss occurred for the methacryl treated laminate, and as a result, the debonding at the fiber/matrix interface and the water penetration into the interface occurred. The degradation of the interface affected the tensile and the impact properties, and it induced the greater modulus and strength reduction. The modulus decreased by only the degradation of the matrix in the amino treated laminate, while it decreased by the degradation of both the matrix and the interface in the methacryl treated laminate. The silane treatment affected the fracture behavior under both the static tensile loading and the impact flexural loading. The long and large scale cracks propagated inside the fiber bundles in the amino treated laminate, while the multiple cracks occurred inside the fiber bundles in the methacryl treated laminate. The fracture mode changed as a result of the debondings inside the fiber bundles due to water immersion in the methacryl treated laminate. The difference in the fracture behavior affected the tensile strength reduction and the change of the impact energy absorption due to the water immersion.

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